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COMPARE AND EVALUATE EXPERIENCE SAMPLING METHOD FORMATS FOR MOBILE SELF-REPORTING OF CURRENT EXPERIENCES

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ABSTRACT

To study the ESM approach, we developed the Mobile AP II system, with which a participant can immediately self-report his/her momentary awareness and experiences using a mobile communication device. Mobile AP II allows a participant to use a mobile phone with recording capability to post his/her momentary awareness and experiences for recording in real time. However, on-site time pressure and operability of mobile phones will affect the transmission and sharing of information to be recorded. Therefore, in this study, we used Mobile AP II (Mobile Activity Probes II) system to carry out an experiment to evaluate the effects of on-site recording formats.

Keywords: Experience Sampling Method, momentary experiences, Mobile AP II.

BACKGROUND

Interactions between humans and different kinds of information are becoming increasingly complicated in today's information-oriented society and ubiquitous communications environment. Detailed information concerning the experiences that comprise users' daily lives and their underlying state of mind is required so that designers/researchers can understand the mechanisms that govern the interactions of these factors. Moreover, much inspiration for design innovation might come from clues obtainable from a deeper knowledge of human thoughts and experiences in daily life. Especially as designed objects and experiences become ubiquitous,

designers/researchers require more information about user-object interactions. This makes it important to devise effective methods to record people's real-life experiences from their own perspective.

EXPERIENCE SAMPLING METHOD

In the study of daily experiences, Csikszentmihalyi, Larson, and Prescott devised the Experience Sampling Method (ESM), which has shown itself to be an effective way to obtain reports of an individual's moment-by-moment experience in real-life situations (Csikszentmihalyi, Larson, & Prescott, 1977). A feature of the ESM approach is that participants can immediately record and evaluate their experiences in their natural environment. This entails the following benefits: (1) discovery of on-site underlying mental states and specific behavior patterns, (2) maintenance of a natural environment, without the sense of tension often produced in laboratories, (3) measurement of concrete behaviors and subjective mental states of participants, without asking hypothetical questions, and (4) obtaining a record of participants' on-site experiences, rather than data derived from their recollection of their own past experiences (Conner, Tennen, Fleeson, & Barrett, 2009; Robins, Fraley, & Krueger, 2007). Therefore, we believe ESM is an effective way to obtain a record of user experiences, including subjective mental states and emotions, at places not suitable for observation. Although ESM is useful as an approach for collecting the above data, this approach is not yet in widespread use due to reasons

such as the cost of tools, convenience, and the burden on participants (Conner, et al., 2009).

MOBILE AP II

For this study, we constructed Mobile Activity Probes II (Mobile AP II, Lin & Okamoto, 2009), which is a system that allows participants to self-report their momentary awareness and experiences using a mobile communication device equipped for the ESM approach. This allows a participant to use the "Sha-Mail" function of their mobile phone to post his/her momentary awareness and experiences to Mobile AP II in real time (Figure 1). By using Mobile AP II in this way, participants do not have to learn how to use new equipment, which will facilitate the posting process. Thus, we hope to decrease compliance problems and improve the quality of participants' descriptions.

Figure 1. Posting to the Mobile AP II system using Sha-Mail. In Japan, Sha-Mail means an email with a camera phone picture attached.

However, as short texts and special grammatical expressions are entered via the usual input for the email function of mobile phones in Japan (Uchida, 2004; Miyake, 2005), this affects the ease of recording and sharing the situational context. Furthermore, during the short on-site recording time, fragmentary records are often made, which also affects the transmission and sharing of information with others. Another problem is that the accuracy of self-reporting varies widely depending on the

participant (Kuniavsky, 2003). Therefore, in this study, we devised the mobile recording technique in situ. This is a reporting format that uses "Sha-Mail" with Mobile AP II and which allows easy recording on-site and easy sharing between researchers/designers and participants. We then evaluated the results.

METHODS

In this study, Mobile AP II provided a reporting format application, the user experience-snapshot format (UX-SP format), to support participants self-reporting including photos and text. The UX-SP format is a semi-structured reporting format that allows participants to report about their awareness on mobile phone in the fieldwork.

We carried out a field experiment using Mobile AP II to evaluate the open-ended format and the UX-SP format (Figure 2). In the open-ended format, no restrictions were imposed on the content to be recorded, and on-site momentary awareness and experiences were recorded freely. In the UX-SP format, participants recorded the following reporting indexes: (1) momentary awareness, (2) explanation of the situation, (3) personal impressions or requests, (4) level of importance 1 to 5 (a number is entered, 5 is the most important), and (5) others. These reporting indexes were displayed automatically on the mobile phone after reading the designated QR code.

PARTICIPANTS

The participants were 24 university students in Japan. They were randomly divided into two groups: the open-ended group (n=12) and the snapshot group (n=12). During the fieldwork, participants used the assigned format to post entries to Mobile AP II.

APPROACH

This study used an event-based design of ESM, which required participants to post pre-defined event experiences relevant to the specified topic of

Figure 2. Reporting formats as they appeared on the mobile phone (left: UX-SP format; right: Open-ended format).

fieldwork as they occurred (Figure 3). Before the experiment, participants received a 'MobileAP2 Card' with a QR code to read the mail address and the format assigned to each group (Figure 4). This saved them the trouble of entering this information. In addition, there was an instruction card specifying the experiences to be sampled. Participants were asked to utilize the specified reporting format to capture photos and text illustrating what they noticed and their experiences in the field and deliver the information to Mobile AP II (see Figure 5). Participants then filled out a questionnaire on their

Figure 3. Fieldwork photos.

Figure 4. MobileAP2 Card.

impressions of the reporting format after the pre- and post-tests. The questionnaire had a total of 15 items, including 5 items each for impressions of the recording work itself, impressions of the recorded content, and general impressions (Table 1). They responded to each item on a 5-point Likert scale.

Impression of the recording work
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ I could finish it fast ▪ I could write clearly ▪ It was easy to summarize ▪ Key points were easy to understand ▪ Communication was easy
Impression of the recorded content
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Specific content ▪ Comprehensive content ▪ Systematic content ▪ Focused content ▪ emotional content
General impression
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ It was fun ▪ It was burdensome ▪ It was easy to record ▪ It was easy to recall ▪ It increased my attention

Table 1. Items used to evaluate subjective impressions

RESULTS

A two-factor analysis of variance was carried out that used the recording groups and pre/post-evaluations as the factors to evaluate the study effects. The results were as follows:

INTERACTION BETWEEN RECORDING GROUPS AND PRE/POST-EVALUATIONS

A significant interaction could be seen between the recording groups and pre/post-evaluations for the

Figure 5. The flow of posting an entry .

item “It was easy to summarize” in the subjective evaluation of the recording work ($F(1, 22) = 5.14, p < .05$), so we verified the simple main effect. In this

Figure 6. Before/after comparison for the item “It was easy to summarize”.

Figure 7. Items displaying a significant difference in terms of the main effect of recording group factors.

Figure 8. Items with a significant difference in terms of the main effect of pre/post-tests.

verification of the simple main effect, no significant difference was found between the recording groups under exercise conditions ($F(1, 22) = 0.00, n.s.$), but a significant post-test difference was shown ($F(1, 22) = 9.32, p < .01$). Furthermore, no significant intergroup difference was seen between pre- and post-test results ($F(1, 22) = 2.57, n.s.$ for both groups). Thus both groups tested the same in the exercise stage, but in the fieldwork (post-test) stage, the snapshot group produced a more favorable evaluation than the open-ended group for the item “It was easy to summarize,” and it was shown that the evaluation of the open-ended group declined from the exercise stage (see Figure 6). We presume this was caused by a feature of the UX-SP format that makes it easier to use than the open-ended format when summarizing experiences in fieldwork environments that produce with different kinds of momentary awareness.

INFLUENCE OF RECORDING GROUPS

The following items in the subjective evaluation of the recording work showed a significant difference in terms of the main effect of recording groups: “I could write clearly” ($F(1, 22) = 12.79, p < .01$) and “Key points were easy to understand” ($F(1, 22) = 7.49, p < .05$). In addition, for the subjective evaluation of the recorded content, “Systematic content” ($F(1, 22) = 11.36, p < .01$) showed a significant difference. Furthermore, for the subjective evaluation of general impression, the item “It was easy to recall” ($F(1, 22) = 5.01, p < .05$) also showed a significant difference. All of these proved that the evaluation of the snapshot group was significantly higher (see Figure 7). These test results suggest that the snapshot group mentioned the effects “I could write clearly” and “Key points were easy to understand” during the recording work because the participants could immediately analyze and record the situation on-site using the UX-SP format items. For this reason, it is possible that the subjective evaluation of systematic content was achieved. We also consider that the systematic content made it easier for participants to recall.

INFLUENCE OF PRE/POST-TESTS

Items that showed significant difference in terms of the main effect of pre/post-tests include “Key points

were easy to understand" ($F(1,22) = 4.40, p < .05$) in the subjective evaluation of the recording work. When exercise and post-test were compared, we could see that exercise was easier to understand than post-test (see Figure 8), but the evaluation for the snapshot group was higher than the open-ended group (open-ended group: pre mean 3.58, post mean 3.25; snapshot group: pre mean 4.25, post mean 3.92). The reason for this can be inferred from a participant's opinion: "I felt uneasy during the fieldwork because I did not know whether the text that I recorded was the kind of information desired by experimenters." Therefore, we believe immediate interactions between designers/researchers and participants during the fieldwork are important to promote postings. On the other hand, a significant difference could be observed in terms of the main effect of pre/post-tests for "Emotional content" in the subjective evaluation of the recorded content ($F(1,22) = 7.76, p < .05$); "It was fun" in the subjective evaluation of general impression ($F(1,22) = 12.44, p < .01$); and "It increased my attention" in the same category ($F(1,22) = 18.33, p < .01$). For these three items, the post-test evaluation was higher (see Figure 8). However, the post-evaluation of "Emotional content" was higher for the open-ended group than the snapshot group (open-ended group: post mean 4.33; snapshot group: post mean 4.25). Therefore, the enhancement of recording emotional content using the UX-SP format will remain as a future issue.

CONCLUSIONS

Collecting user experience data plays an important role in the early stages of design, especially the highly interactive product design or service design. However, recording a good-quality user experience with self-reporting remains difficult. In this study, these results indicate that the UX-SP format could improve certain writing skills, such as content and self-reflection, while participants report moment-by-moment experiences in real life. We also found that the use of the UX-SP format, as opposed to just reporting subjective thoughts, may have helped study participants to quickly summarize the context of events related to their moment-by-moment experiences.

Using the UX-SP format helped to produce a more definitive recorded summary of the context of an event, especially when participants were asked to break the details of an event down into a number of reporting indexes, than when they were asked to report the event experience rather freely. Even though they used snippets of sentences or phrases to report on each item in the UX-SP format, the context of an event could be systematically understood and analyzed. Moreover, these pictures and snippets allowed the experiences to be retrieved and remembered easily later on. The results reflected in part the way in which the data were recorded with the UX-SP format.

In the future, we hope to provide more detailed results, and intend to continue pursuing the investigation of ESM to use the mobile environment in a series of experimental studies.

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